

A MODEL FOR IMPROVING THE COMPETENCE OF MANAGEMENT OF EXECUTIVE PERSONNEL IN THE SPHERE OF DIGITIZATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article provides detailed information about the formation of management competence of the head of an educational institution, the role of modeling, the way of modeling allows you to visually, figuratively present a pedagogical phenomenon in the form of an integral dynamic system using diagrams, concise verbal characteristics.*

Keywords: *competence, respondent, individual, subject, empathy, object, component, objectb component, emotional component, reflexive component, cognitive-operative, personal-semantic.*

One of the urgent problems of vocational education in the last decade has been the formation of management competence of heads of educational institutions, the determination of its place in the professional training process of specialists in the system of professional development. Our research shows that many of the leaders of Kuzbass educational institutions (87% of the total number of respondents) feel the need to master management competence. In order to satisfy the professional obligations of the heads of educational institutions, it is necessary to create conditions for the purposeful formation of the management powers of the heads of educational institutions in the system of professional development. In the scientific literature, there are different approaches to describing this concept, which characterize the professional skills of the head of an educational institution. It is closely related to the concepts of "competence" and "professional competence of the head of an educational institution". Let's analyze these concepts.

The concept of "competence" in the "dictionary of foreign word interpretation" has two meanings:

- 1) qualification;
- 2) having knowledge allows you to judge something.

Success as a field of knowledge or practice is defined by a "logical dictionary-reference", in which a known (competent) person has a lot of specific knowledge and practical experience. If an individual has the necessary competencies, then his state of development is characterized by the term "competence".

Thus, Y.V. Vardanyan believes that competence is the desire and ability of an individual to use their theoretical knowledge and practical experience to solve certain problems,[1]. Another approach to the definition of this concept is N.L. Dmitrieva. He considers competence as a personal quality or a set of qualities that possess it (a person) and as a minimal experience associated with activities in a particular field.[2] N.N. Koshel believes that competence is the ability not only to act but to act effectively, "knowledge of the problem";[3] A.I. Panarin argues that there is knowledge, skills, and willingness to practice these skills in his work;[4] J. Raven considers

competence to be the sum of knowledge, skills, and competencies that manifest in an activity that is personally relevant to the subject, the ability necessary to perform.[5]

The concept of "competence" is defined as an individual psychological characteristic that expresses the willingness of the subject to master various types of activities and to carry them out successfully. It appears that the manifestation of competence occurs when the subject has a certain potential, becomes realized in practical activity, and can be a guarantee that the activity being carried out is effective. In other words, some authors see in this concept the presence of certain knowledge for successful activities, others believe that competence is not only the ability to work, but also the organization and systematic understanding of all problems associated with activities, a complex system of an internal psychological system. Such ambivalence of these definitions, in our opinion, is associated with the pedagogical and psychological components of the concept of "competence". We consider competence from these two positions and follow the following interpretation of this concept: competence is a set of knowledge, skills, abilities and experience that is manifested in the personally important activities of the subject. Many authors (N.I.Zaprudsky, Y.F.Zeyer, A.V.Khutorskoy et al.) define professional competence as a system of knowledge and skills, professionally significant personal qualities that provide the ability to perform professional tasks at a certain level.[6] At the same time, other researchers (A.I.Akhulkova, L.N.Nikitina, A.I.Panarin et al.) connects this concept with the ability and readiness to carry out professional activities, in particular pedagogical ones.[7] Let's analyze the legality of this connection. The psychological-pedagogical Dictionary defines abilities as "individual psychological characteristics that are subjective conditions for the successful implementation of a particular type of activity." They are found in the speed, depth and strength of mastering the methods and methods of activity. The presence of professional competence of a specialist determines the readiness to carry out professional activities, which is a necessary component of professional competence.

It follows from the analysis of the above interpretations of the concept of "readiness" with respect to professional activity that it can be considered in two ways: mental state and the quality of personality. Such an interpretation of readiness attracts us, and we take it into account in the interpretation of the essence of professional competence. At the same time, we can conclude from the above that it is wrong to simultaneously associate professional competence with ability and training, since, according to many researchers, it involves the ability to prepare for the implementation of professional activities. Thus, we consider professional competence as a set of necessary professional knowledge, skills, experiences, personal qualities of professional importance and willingness to apply them practically.

Let's reveal the meaning of the concept of "professional competence of the head of an educational institution". Literature analysis shows that among the many different opinions and approaches of researchers, three perspectives on this concept can be distinguished conditionally. The opinions of scientists who look at this concept in terms of a traditional approach to the first Group (M.V.Bastrikov, I.V.Grishina, A.S.Makarenko, T.I.Shamova, S.T.Shatsky).[8] A.S. Makarenko, S.T. Shatsky indicates in his works that the heads of educational institutions should have professional competence, that is, have knowledge about the modern problems of pedagogy and psychology, about the scientific foundations of school management, and be able to apply this knowledge in practice. At the same time, the authors include knowledge in the concept of "professional competence of the head of an educational institution" and the ability to apply them

in practice. T.I. Shamova, describing the professional competence of the head of the educational institution, expands the list of knowledge and requirements: she must have a complex of scientific knowledge and skills of a professional nature. In addition, T.I. Shamova emphasizes that this is knowledge of the latest achievements in the field of psychology, pedagogy, management theory, law, sociology, School Hygiene; this is the creative use of knowledge, respect for other people's opinions and the ability to conduct dialogue, discussion politely and reliably.[9]

Based on the analysis of the above points, it can be concluded that in the second group, the content of the concept of “professional competence of the head of an educational institution” is considered from the point of view of the activity approach, since its main characteristic is activity for the implementation of certain functions. The opinions of both groups of scientists are of a common nature yega, since this content of the concept indicates that it belongs to the profession of the manager and is his professional and personal characteristic.

It can be understood as the ability and preparation of the leader to identify, correctly formulate, make a holistic and in-depth analysis of the problems of the educational institution and find appropriate ways to solve them. He concludes that the basis of the management authority of the head of the educational institution will be the professional competence of the head of the educational institution, which will make it possible to make appropriate requirements for management activities. The concepts of “management competence of the head of an educational institution and “professional competence of the head of an educational institution” can be considered as two different and interconnected concepts.

L.G.Kiseleva considers the management authority of the head of an educational institution to be a personal and professional feature in terms of a competency-based approach, including the willingness and ability to professionally perform management functions that should ensure effective solution of professional problems.[10] "Management Authority of the head of an educational institution" ability and readiness to perform management functions, but the authors call the composition of the functions different; on the general side, the result of performing these functions should be an immersion in the tasks associated with the activity or development of an educational institution. We note that these researchers consider the concepts of "professional competence of the head of an educational institution" and "management competence of the head of an educational institution" to be two different, but interrelated, and the management competence of the head of an organization. the educational institution is a component of its professional competence.

The content of the concept of" managerial competence of the head of an educational institution "coincides with the content of the concept of" professional competence of the head of an educational institution". That is,"professional competence of the head of an educational institution"is a broader concept, rather than the concept of" managerial competence of the head of an educational institution", it involves the readiness of the head to effectively carry out various types of activities, including management. We consider the management competence of the head of an educational institution as the readiness of the head to effectively perform management functions based on theoretical knowledge and practical skills, experience, individual personal qualities, a reasonable aspiration to achieve the goal and solve the tasks.

One of the tasks of modern higher education is the formation of management competence of university graduates. This is because management is a universal means of organizing professional activities on the principles of consistency, purposefulness, flexibility, diagnostics,

efficiency, etc. Consequently, the problem of the formation of management competence of undergraduate students in the direction of pedagogical education remains relevant, which makes it possible to ensure effective management of educational institutions in the future.

We understand the willingness of an individual to carry out management activities effectively as functional competence. There is a set of "constant components (motivation, Goal Setting, Information basis of activity, forecasting its results, decision-making, planning, programming, control, correction, set of actions to be performed) that are objective in the structure of any activity. The first component of the structure of activity is motivation, which is considered in the context of creating an internal motivation for action in modern conditions. The head of an educational organization should not only have a personal motive for the formation of managerial competence and the effective implementation of managerial actions, but also create a more developed management system, therefore, we have introduced a motivational-targeted component into the structure.

The main component of the management competence structure is the activity component, which determines the readiness of the manager to perform management functions (information-analytical, planning-prognostic, organizational and control-diagnostic).[11] The result of the activity depends on the completeness and quality of the formation of the qualifications (actions in a specific situation) of the leader, the degree of mastery of the methods of activity, the degree of readiness to perform certain actions. In each case, the basis of practical skills is theoretical knowledge and experience, therefore, we included in the management competence of the head of the educational institution a cognitive component that determines the knowledge necessary for management activities. Of great importance in management activities is the ability to self-assessment and introspection, so we have included a reflexive component in the composition of management competence.

Speaking about the formation of management competence of the head of an educational institution, it is worth noting in particular the role of modeling in this process. The modeling method allows you to visually, figuratively present a pedagogical phenomenon in the form of an integral dynamic system using diagrams, concise verbal characteristics. The creation of the model is a concretization of the general scientific principle of the connection between integrity and the individual, in which their harmony and the resulting interaction give rise to a new quality – the desired model. The peculiarities of the formation of management competence of students of a pedagogical higher educational institution require the use of a model with components, Structure and content of management competence, stages and conditions of its implementation, which ensure the effectiveness of this model. The model for the formation of management competence that we have developed is a holistic, open, dynamic pedagogical system with many descriptions of the characteristics characteristic of pedagogical systems - integrity, structure, hierarchy, system and environment.

By the formation of management competence of the future head of an educational institution, we understand the formation of readiness for management activities in terms of an axiological approach based on the general concept of "value setting". According to L.V.Vedernikova, "this conclusion makes it possible to consider the process of formation of managerial competence as a whole, as a process of formation of readiness for managerial activity or as a process of formation of thinking for managerial activity."[12] He argues, "... professional

position can be expressed as a system of value relations in three areas: knowledge, action and experience". Thus, we can highlight specific aspects of readiness for management activities:

1) acquisition of knowledge, that is, the direction of value to personal knowledge and understanding;

2) activity, that is, the direction of value for cooperation;

3) empathy, that is, the direction of value to empathy;

4) analysis, that is, the value setting for reflection.

A valuable understanding of the content of readiness for management activities allows us to identify the components of the process of forming management skills, which include:

1. The object component denotes the acquisition of knowledge and is formed in the field of knowledge, in which theoretical knowledge and the ability to apply them in practice are the most important.

2. The social component is formed in practical activities and indicates the readiness of the subjects of the educational process for cooperation in management activities.

3. The emotional component determines the attitude to management activities and is formed within the framework of the experience that determines the attitude of value towards the subjects of the educational process and is manifested in the empathic behavior of the future head of the educational institution.

4. The reflexive component is also formed in the field of experience and is associated with the need to assess the managerial activity of an individual.

In our eyes, the formation of management competence of the leader is carried out as follows:

- cognitive-operative, in which the main indicators are the completeness and efficiency of knowing the theory and practice of management;

- personal-activity, in which the main indicator is readiness for interaction, dialogue of the positions of the subjects of the interaction of management;

- personal-semantic, in which the indicators are tolerance, empathy;

- evaluator, in which the main indicator is readiness for thinking.”[13]

The selected criteria and indicators can be used to determine the levels of formation of managerial qualifications of the heads of future educational institutions. A low level is the presence of knowledge in management theory, but the lack of skills to apply this knowledge in practice, or their partial use in standard situations, that is, management activities are understood as a set of separate operations that do not have a common goal.

Intermediate level-on the basis of the analysis and generalization of theoretical knowledge, the master forms the skill of using them in practice, that is, “individual skills for understanding their actions and capabilities, regulation of management are formed. Management activities at this level are the solution of theoretical situations and practical management problems for the student, the implementation of a number of management functions that are interconnected, taking into account the personal characteristics of the subjects of the educational process.

A higher degree-a graduate student becomes a subject of goal-setting, he is able to find effective means of implementing the values and goals of management. At the same time, the interaction of the subjects of the pedagogical process taking into account personal values in the context of the adoption of management - Subject-subject relations. At this level, the managerial activity of the future head of the educational institution is the effective interaction of the subjects

of the pedagogical process and the adoption of managerial decisions in accordance with the subject-subject relationship. Thus, the generalization of the above allows us to note that the model for the formation of managerial competence of undergraduate students in the direction of "pedagogical education" is a specific standard of managerial activity that should be formulated in the context of pedagogical education.

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